

Development of Pictographic Odia-Odia Baby Term Dictionary for Understanding Language Utterance

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Abstract

The secret of language development in children is talking together a lot and listening a lot. It supports child's ability to communicate, express and understand feelings. In their first twelve months babies are most likely coo and laugh, play with sounds and begin to communicate with gestures like waving. Babbling is an important developmental stage during the first year and followed by 'jargon phrases.' At the age of one and half year, children often say their first words with meaning. And the first three years of life kids keep developing language skills where learning to understand, use and enjoy language is the critical first step in this stage. Therefore the kid terms or baby terms from whole of the language learning can't be separated. Though it is changing in nature, it is required to collect those terms in order to understand language learning. In this paper, we try to make a baby term dictionary by collecting such terms from Odia language mother tongue kids.

Keywords: Pictographic, Dictionary, Odia language, Baby term, Odia graphics

1. Introduction

Every kid is uniquely special and brilliant. The richness of a language can be measured by having a look at its store of vocabulary. The number of vocabularies developed in a language speaks about the advancement of the language. If a particular language produces a number of dictionaries, it can be taken as the basis of knowing the strength and weakness of its vocabulary. There are different kinds of dictionaries available online and offline (printed version). Some of the dictionaries deal with the mapping of words from one language to other language. There are also dictionaries that work within the same language like Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary that gives the meaning of an English word with another simplified word expression. There are many countries that have their own dictionary to translate foreign language to their local language and vice versa. It helps them to learn and understand the foreign language in an easy way. Therefore, dictionary plays the biggest role in translating one language to the others; it is one means of understanding the culture of the language.

However, Pictures and their description makes lasting impression on the learning undertaken by the kids. Through Pictures kids enrich their vocabulary and the learning ability. As picture

illustrates the context more clearly than the written form of words, therefore the kids' dictionary needs to be appealing. Again, irrespective of erroneous pronunciation from a standard language, the term of a baby carries the meaning and through this the baby communicates among his near and dear ones. Hence the baby terms cannot be excluded from ambit of a language. Therefore here we are proposing to develop a Pictographic Baby Term Dictionary preferably in Monolingual. First looking our research area here we consider carrying forward our research to our native language Odia and wants to develop the Odia-Odia monolingual dictionary that will display the meaning of the word with multimedia content that can describe more about the word and its meaning. The dictionary will display the meaning of the word with multimedia content. Multimedia is an application that uses multiple modalities to their advantages including text, image, drawing/graphics, animation, video and sound. Displaying the meaning of the word with different multimedia content will help the users to understand the meaning of the word very easily. The sound/voice support helps the user to know how the word is pronounced correctly; picture also describes the meaning of the word better than text i.e. "a picture worth more than 1000 words".

2. Objectives and Scope

To develop a Pictographic Odia-Odia Baby Term Multimedia dictionary that could analyze, design and displaying mechanism for Odia baby terms. This dictionary can be used as a: (a) A Quick reference tool; (b) Language recorder; (c) Language standardize; (d) Vocabulary builder.

3. Literature Survey

The New Oxford Picture Dictionary (1988) illustrates over 2400 terms and caters as a unique language learning tool for English Language learners, The chronological study of origin and development of study of Odia language from 1811 to 2012 covering 202 years reveals that the Odia language has the credit of producing more than 300 dictionaries, classified into different categories, like Monolingual dictionaries (Odia-Odia) covering 113, Bilingual (Odia-English) 32, (English-Odia) 74, (English-Odia) glossary 54, dialectical dictionaries 21, Dictionaries of Proverbs (Odia-Odia and Odia-English) 50 and Dictionary of Quotations about 20. In order to find out the decadal trend and growth pattern of publication of dictionaries, the entire period is divided into 10 years barring the last one, covering 12 years. Out of these:

“Vocabulary of Oriya and English for the use of students” published by Muhan Persad Takoor. It was printed at Serampore Mission Press in 1811. This dictionary is containing 4246 words. And it claims as the first and foremost position among the dictionaries of Odia language.

The other notable dictionaries in Odia language are (a) Puma Chandra Bhasha Kosha (1940) by G.C. Praharaj, (b) Pramod Abhidhan (1942,2011) by Pramod Chandra Deb Pattayat, (c) Shabda Sindhu (2008) by Natabar Satapathy, (d) Odia Bhasha Kosha (1997,2007) by Sarat Chandra Behera and others, (e) Odia Biswakosha Darpana (1989) by Dinabandhu Biswal and Krupasindhu Biswal, (f) Tarun Sabdakosha (1966) by Krushna Chandra, (g) Dharma Sindhu Sabda Kosha (2012) by Kshiroda Parija and (h) Odia Sahitya Kosha (1998) by Bainshidhar Biswal.

4. Some Odia Baby Terms

Baby terms are special terms, which are only best understood by the mother of the child, i.e. the speaker or vice versa i.e. where mother is the speaker and child is the listener. There is an unwritten language of communication or the literature developed in between mother and her child where every child is special. The kids' language has no fear, violence or threat but lots of fun, happiness, jokes, love and smile are the cream components. Here some collected baby terms are presented. These are as under.

Sl. No.	Odia Baby Terms	Standard Odia Terms	Meaning in English
01.	ଚକି (chaki)	ଚକଲେଟ୍ (Chocklet)	Chocklet
02.	କୁଟୁ (Kutu)	ବିସ୍କୁଟ୍ (Biscuit)	Biscuit
03.	କପଳ (KapaLa)	ଚପଳ (Chapala)	Shoes
04.	କକ (Kaka)	କୁକୁର (Kukura)	Dog
05.	ମେଉଁ (meun)	ବିଲେଇ (Bilei)	Cat
06.	କୁକୁ (kuku)	କଜ୍ଜଳ (Kajwala)	Black
07.	ତୁଉକୁ ମୁଷି (TuUku Musi)	ଗୁଣ୍ଡୁଚି ମୁଷା (Gunduchi Musa)	Squirrel
08.	କମ୍ବଳ (Kambal)	ଚଦର (Chadara)	Woolen Cloth
09.	ହାମା (Hama)	ଗାଈ (Gai)	Cow
10.	ହାଉଁ କରିବା (Haum Kariba)	ଖାଇବା (Khaibaa)	Eat

5. System Work Plan/ Methodology

However, the real constraint is to take the first lexicographic decisions and the methodology of baby term data collection. As for the participants in the activity, we decided to involve the babies of 3 to 5 years old in order to capture the terminological variation. The proposed dictionaries were going to be developed through Odia baby speakers through a participation of Rapid Word Collection workshop at Odisha. During this carefully structured workshop, community members (mother tongue speakers of the language) collect words from their baby-speakers of the Odia language, prompted by questions related to a selection of semantic domains (families of closely-related words). The nearly 1,000 domains can be grouped into nine main categories: Person, Language and thought, Social behavior, Daily life, Physical actions, etc.

This focused effort to collect words is one of DDP's most notable strengths. In the past, a researcher might make note of a few new words each day while engaged in language learning or language development activities. The community can continue adding to the dictionary and work toward publishing it in a format that meets their needs.

- **Robustness:** All user input shall be verified and checked for its correctness and completeness before it is passed as a parameter for further execution at the server side, therefore the system can be protected from failures that may occur from invalid user inputs.
- **Reliability:** The system shall be tested after and during the development process to verify that the specified services are available on different client platforms. And also it should give consistent and correct output for various types of input it is given.
- **Availability:** The system shall be installed in an individual Personal Computer.
- **Usability:** The system shall be developed to be easy for user understanding. Especially in developing the user interface it is better to keep the baby user dictionary in mind.

6. Conclusion

The famous psychologist Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory believes that thinking was different during each stage of development and children naturally attempt to understand what they do not know. It is important to stress that in present dictionary actively babies can play as "authors" of their terms for dictionary designed, where if we are those responsible for its final editing. Again meaning developed for a particular lexicon may vary from one author i.e. baby to baby or mother to mother. Where, priorities are to be given to ascertain certain meanings of the words.

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